

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D3.1 GOhydro Data Platform v2.0

GOhydro is part of the ERA-NET Cofund ICT-AGRI-FOOD with funding provided by national sources [i.e., General Secretariat for Research and Innovation in Greece, Ministry of Environment and Food in Denmark, Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture in Germany and the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania] and co-funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, Grant Agreement number 862665.

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D3.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE	GOhydro Data Platform v2.0
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
PROJECT ACRONYM	GOhydro
PROJECT FULL NAME	A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units
STARTING DATE (DUR.)	01/03/2021 (24 months)
ENDING DATE	28/02/2023
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://www.gohydro.org/
COORDINATOR	Panagiotis Zervas
COORDINATOR EMAIL	panagiotis@scio.systems
WORKPACKAGE N. TITLE	WP3 DATA-DRIVEN PLATFORM FOR VERTICAL FARMING
WORKPACKAGE LEADER	SCiO
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR EMAIL	antonis@scio.systems
DATE OF DELIVERY (CONTRACTUAL)	31/05/2023
DATE OF DELIVERY (SUBMITTED)	31/05/2023
VERSION STATUS	V1.0
NATURE	Demonstrator
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public
AUTHORS (PARTNER)	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO), Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)
CONTRIBUTORS	-
REVIEWER	Eleni Makarona (NCSR-D)

VERSION	MODIFICATION(S)	DATE	AUTHOR(S)
0.1	Initial ToC developed	19.04.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
0.5	First version ready	07.05.2023	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)
0.8	Updates and input to first version	20.05.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
0.9	Updates based on the internal review	28.05.2023	Eleni Makarona (NCSR-D)
1.0	Final version ready	31.05.2023	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)

PARTICIPANTS		CONTACT PERSON
<p>SCiO P.C. (SCiO, Greece) Coordinator</p>		<p>Panagiotis Zervas Email: panagiotis@scio.systems</p>
<p>Department of Plant and Environmental Sciences, University of Copenhagen (UCPH, Denmark)</p>		<p>Bhim Bahadur Ghaley Email: bbg@plen.ku.dk</p>
<p>Holisun SRL (Holisun, Romania)</p>		<p>Oliviu Matei Email: oliviu.matei@holisun.com</p>
<p>nr21 DESIGN GmbH (nr21 DESIGN, Germany)</p>		<p>Niklas Galler Email: niklas.galler@nr21.com</p>
<p>Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos” (NCSR-D, Greece)</p>		<p>Eleni Makarona Email: e.makarona@inn.demokritos.gr</p>
<p>Department of Technical and Soil Sciences, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca (USAMV, Romania)</p>		<p>Teodor Rusu Email: trusu@usamvcluj.ro</p>

ACRONYMS LIST

API	Application Programming Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
CSU	Communication and Storage Unit

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES.....	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	7
1 INTRODUCTION.....	8
2 DATA PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE.....	9
2.1 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN.....	9
2.2 CORE PLATFORM COMPONENTS.....	10
2.2.1 Pre-processing Pipeline.....	10
2.2.2 AI Pipeline.....	10
2.2.3 Persistence Layer.....	11
2.2.4 GOhydro API.....	11
3 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS.....	13

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure Number	Figure Caption
Figure 1	GOhydro Data Platform Architecture
Figure 2	Sample JSON object sent from the CSU to the data platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report accompanies the second deployment of the GOhydro Data Platform, focusing on the provision of details for the implemented APIs for data importing to and exposing from the platform.

It also summarizes the incorporated technologies and frameworks for operationalising the different parts of the platform.

Further updates on the platform will be reflected on the documentation accompanying the platform's software, available via the repositories hosting the platform's codebase.

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro aims to develop a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in any hydroponic installation. In the bigger picture, the project aspires to culminate in the production of a radical platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all and user-friendly tool applicable to all forms of urban farming.

Towards this objective, data management and analysis is crucial for the accurate, timely and secure production and presentation of insights to the grower, via easy to use interfaces. In this context, WP3 aims to put in place the infrastructure that will realise the data storage and analytics functions required by the platform, develop, train and deploy the AI components that will power the recommendation and decision support features, and build the user-facing applications that will provide access to the data collected from a GOhydro installation along with the recommendations to the human managing the installation.

D3.1 deals with the design and development of the data infrastructure that will fulfil the aforementioned data requirements. The data platform is built using established and well-supported storage and programmatic frameworks, over which the data ingestion, organisation, indexing and searching functionalities required by the project are applied. The deliverable also entails the implementation of the API mechanisms that will allow the usage of the platform through client apps, like the GOHYDRO mobile application.

The first version of the deliverable summarized the architectural and technical choices for implementing and deploying the platform, in accordance with the requirements posed by the scientific analysis of hydroponic growing and the data provided by the sensing solutions integrated in the GOhydro unit.

The present report is an update of document accompanying the first version, providing further details mainly on the established APIs for communicating with the hydroponic unit and for exposing data to client applications, including the GOhydro mobile app.

2 DATA PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

2.1 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

No significant changes were deemed necessary in comparison to the initial version of the data platform. As a reminder, the overall architecture of the data platform is depicted in Figure 1 and analysed below.

Figure 1: GOhydro Data Platform Architecture

As discussed in the relevant deliverable D2.1, the communication point with the hydroponic installation is the Communication and Storage Unit (CSU) incorporated in the installation. The CSU collects data from all sensing nodes included in a given installation and exposes via the appropriate APIs the collected data for further processing.

The data collected by the CSU are sent as JSON objects in the Quantum platform to undergo further analysis by the Quantum Pipelines for Pre-processing and Analysis. A sample JSON sent by the CSU to the platform is depicted in Figure 2.

```

{
  "_id": {
    "$oid": "62de56fd2c34c9459e31002b"
  },
  "controller_id": "E4:5F:01:47:4C:71",
  "data_kits": [
    {
      "sensor_kit_id": "B8:27:EB:62:F9:40",
      "data_points": [
        {
          "sensor": "PH_Meter",
          "value": "2.80",
          "timestamp": "2022-07-25T11:40:26"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
    
```

```
}
{
  "sensor": "Air_Humidity",
  "value": "52.18",
  "timestamp": "2022-07-25T11:40:26"
},
{
  "sensor": "TDS_Meter",
  "value": "1.44",
  "timestamp": "2022-07-25T11:40:26"
},
{
  "sensor": "Water_Temperature",
  "value": "26.11",
  "timestamp": "2022-07-25T11:40:26"
},
{
  "sensor": "Air_Temperature",
  "value": "26.06",
  "timestamp": "2022-07-25T11:40:26"
},
{
  "sensor": "UV_light",
  "value": "0.02",
  "timestamp": "2022-07-25T11:40:26"
}
]
}
```

Figure 2: Sample JSON object sent from the CSU to the data platform

Communication between the pipeline components is implemented through the use of an Apache Kafka infrastructure for message passing via a message bus monitored by all components. The components included in the pipeline are described in the following subsection.

2.2 CORE PLATFORM COMPONENTS

2.2.1 Pre-processing Pipeline

The pre-processing modules of the platform will be responsible for the preparation of the incoming data streams before further analysis is possible. On the one hand, the components deal with the identification and annotation/elimination of outlier measurements and identification of gaps in measurement timeseries. On the other hand, harmonization components are responsible for transforming the input data in the representation that will be used for ingesting them in the appropriate persistent storage mechanism from the ones described in the relevant section.

2.2.2 AI Pipeline

The AI Pipeline encapsulates all modules responsible for the analysis of the incoming data towards producing predictions and recommendations for optimizing cultivation in the hydroponic unit. The modules are organised under a workflow that facilitates their re-training in timely intervals as more data and analyses become available, minimising the effort for training, validating and re-deploying the trained models. The models are described in further detail in the relevant D3.2 deliverable.

2.2.3 Persistence Layer

The GOhydro persistence layer incorporates three different storage technologies, to serve different data functions and requirements for the operation of the platform.

A **Relational Database** solution (MySQL) is used for storing platform-specific data for operations like user management, device registration and status monitoring, etc.

A **NoSQL Database** (MongoDB) is used for storing the raw measurement timeseries as delivered by the CSU and exported by the pre-processing pipeline.

2.2.4 GOhydro API

The GOhydro API defines the REST calls for importing data to the platform and exposing data and analysis results to client applications. The API ensures safe communication and controlled access to the data by the GOhydro mobile application and third-party tools in the future. The API is implemented in PHP, using the Laravel framework. It incorporates the following calls.

Call	/configuration
Type	GET
Parameters	CSU ID
Description	Returns the configuration parameters for the specified CSU, namely the devices controlled by the CSU and the set interval for data collection
Sample response	<pre> { "_id": { "timestamp": 1657623485, "date": 1657623485000 }, "controller_id": "E4:5F:01:47:4C:71", "devices": [{ "device_id": "B8:27:EB:2C:B8:9D", "function": "active", "sampling_rate": "60" }] } </pre>

Call	/configure
Type	POST
Description	<p>The call submits configuration information for an installation to the GOhydro cloud infrastructure. The configuration parameters entail:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The identifier (MAC address) of the Controller - The identifier(s) (MAC address(es)) of the Sensor Kits bound to the Controller - The set interval that defines the frequency of data submission from the Sensor Kit to the Controller and from the Controller to the Cloud Infrastructure.
Sample input	<pre> { "controller_id": "E4:5F:01:5F:63:CX", </pre>

```

"devices": [
  {
    "device_id": "B8:27:EB:62:F9:4X",
    "function": "active",
    "sampling_rate": "90"
  }
]
    
```

Call	/data
Type	GET
Parameters	CSU ID
Description	Returns the data and analysis results associated with the devices controlled by the specified CSU

Call	/save
Type	POST
Description	Sends the data collected by the devices controlled by the sending CSU and not yet submitted and imported to the data platform

3 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

The report serves as an informative document accompanying the second version of the GOhydro data platform prototype. The report will accompany the relevant software and be accordingly updated as technical provisions continue to mature. Updated versions will be available through the relevant code repositories where the codebase of the different platform components are stored.